

Q1 Prior to this Hackathon, how would you describe your level of experience with containers?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Experienced	0.00% 0
Intermediate	16.67% 2
Somewhat	58.33% 7
Inexperienced	25.00% 3
TOTAL	12

Q2 Which approaches, if any, to containerization have you used in the past?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

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ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
OpenVZ	0.00% 0
LXC	0.00% 0
Docker	66.67% 8
CoreOS/rkt	0.00% 0
Podmad	0.00% 0
Singularity	16.67% 2
Charlie Cloud	0.00% 0
Shifter	0.00% 0
Sarus	8.33% 1
Total Respondents: 12	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	none	12/9/2019 4:43 PM
2	None	12/9/2019 10:58 AM

Q3 After the Hackathon, how comfortable do you feel about continuing your work using Docker-compatible containers

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

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ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Very comfortable: I can continue without much support	66.67%	8
Somewhat comfortable: I will need a bit of continued support	33.33%	4
Not yet comfortable: I will need considerable support	0.00%	0
TOTAL		12

Q4 Did you manage to create a Docker container with your simulation code?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	58.33%	7
No	0.00%	0
If yes, how did you like them?	41.67%	5
TOTAL		12

#	IF YES, HOW DID YOU LIKE THEM?	DATE
1	it was very interesting to run the simulation with docker.	12/9/2019 4:43 PM
2	Yes, it was very simple to use. I like it we will switch to Docker	12/9/2019 12:45 PM
3	They are practical means of deploying build dependencies and code to collaborators	12/9/2019 10:58 AM
4	Relatively easy. I was surprised by the computational performance achieved by the container against the native compiled code	12/9/2019 10:29 AM
5	Great work; all our containers are re-usable as is. It will facilitate our model developments; we installed sarus on a small virtual machine and we requested our national provider to install it on the national HPC.	12/9/2019 9:41 AM

Q5 Briefly describe the two biggest challenges you faced in the process of creating a container for your code

Answered: 10 Skipped: 2

#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	1) We lost just one container layer in between by the import of the docker container in Sarus 2) Build time of the application within the container was very large (to be done on notebooks) which made testing / debugging time consuming	12/20/2019 6:35 PM
2	to adapt the code and compile	12/12/2019 9:47 AM
3	Splitting the application workflow	12/10/2019 2:52 PM
4	adjusting my code to run inside container since logging was generated in teh same folder, and by running it inside teh container, log files were deleted. Waiting time to upload images, sometimes more than 30 -40 minutes to Piz Daint through wirless.	12/9/2019 4:43 PM
5	since our code is the CMIP6 production code, it has a lot of dependencies and possibles sets. Creat an small case with all settings acoording was the biggest challege	12/9/2019 12:45 PM
6	The first challenge was inconsistencies in Linux virtual environments regarding already installed packages. The second was resolving local hostnames for running MPI.	12/9/2019 10:58 AM
7	No specific challenges, or in other words, we encountered the same problems that we face in when installing a complex code and its dependencies	12/9/2019 10:29 AM
8	no challenges in particular	12/9/2019 10:26 AM
9	challenge-1: interfacing our scripts with Slurm & sarus; challenge-2: understanding OCI hooks and how sarus use Idconfig to "remap" mpi libraries from the docker to the native MPI libraries.	12/9/2019 9:41 AM
10	Our simulation code (ICON) is not ready to be launched in an MPI environment with containers due to how the input-data is handled. We therefore had to introduce some daint-specific things. This could be resolved by abstracting how ICON experiments are set up.	12/6/2019 11:17 AM

Q6 Where did you hear about the hackathon

Answered: 10 Skipped: 2

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#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	Carlos Osuna (via ESiWACE)	12/20/2019 6:42 PM
2	BSC	12/12/2019 9:48 AM
3	ESiWACE meetings	12/10/2019 2:53 PM
4	ESiWACE newsletter	12/9/2019 4:48 PM
5	Email	12/9/2019 12:49 PM
6	ESiWACE2 community	12/9/2019 11:03 AM
7	During the ESiWACE2 General Assembly	12/9/2019 10:33 AM
8	from a co-worker at CMCC foundation	12/9/2019 10:30 AM
9	Google search: HPC + container; at some point I found info about shifter and was directed to CSCS; a few more search and I found the hackathon on EsiWACE.	12/9/2019 9:54 AM
10	From my employer (MeteoSwiss)	12/6/2019 11:19 AM

Q7 Tell us something we did right...

Answered: 10 Skipped: 2

#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	It was great to have container experts from CSCS with us and perfect organization	12/20/2019 6:42 PM
2	everything was right, very well organized	12/12/2019 9:48 AM
3	Providing excellent coaching	12/10/2019 2:53 PM
4	All experiences were excellent. If I want to pinpoint the best thing, it would be the full engagement of the project mentors in all three days with us. It helped us to be able to deliver a complete product at the end of the third day.	12/9/2019 4:48 PM
5	The organization in general, the templates to write the report, THE FOOD!, HPC queue and set.	12/9/2019 12:49 PM
6	Organisation was great and mentors very knowledgeable and helpful.	12/9/2019 11:03 AM
7	Perfect organization of the event, excellent the idea to have an expert as mentor for each group	12/9/2019 10:33 AM
8	impeccable organization	12/9/2019 10:30 AM
9	For me it was perfect: right timing; right content; perfect outcome. Very skilled staff. And very good food (I loved the fruits for break time) and good coffee!!!	12/9/2019 9:54 AM
10	Having our personal mentor (Rafael) working WITH us all the time was extremely beneficial	12/6/2019 11:19 AM

Q8 Tell us something we could improve:

Answered: 10 Skipped: 2

2019 ESiWACE2 Container Hackathon for Modellers

#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	The hackathon room had to be closed quite early in the evening	12/20/2019 6:42 PM
2	maybe some more social activities post hackathon so people have the chance to socialize and get know each other a bit better	12/12/2019 9:48 AM
3	Encouraging inter-group exchange of experience	12/10/2019 2:53 PM
4	To be honest, I had an excellent experince. Maybe if I want to be very picky, I would say internet connection was slow for uploading docker images sometimes more than 3,4 Gb, which sometimes took more than 30 min to be transferred to Daint.	12/9/2019 4:48 PM
5	keep the accounts more time to contitue (maybe one more week), more clear the way that the code should put in the container, I don't realize how to do it until the first day	12/9/2019 12:49 PM
6	One thing to perhaps think about is how to incorporate containerisation tools into systems where a) environment modules are used for managing build dependencies and b) users do not have "sudo" rights. I am aware this is not really within the scope of the workshop, however it is a situation in which many researchers work.	12/9/2019 11:03 AM
7	-	12/9/2019 10:33 AM
8	I don't know	12/9/2019 10:30 AM
9	I did not really have time to discuss with other teams (I am not part of ESiWACE so I did not know any of them; or one or two only). Maybe on the first day, organizers could have suggested attendees to self-organize a dinner together (I mean I did not expect locals to join or organize but just to suggest); I guess we were all a bit tired on day-1 and having to leave the room quickly did not help.	12/9/2019 9:54 AM
10	The venue should be open longer than 9-5	12/6/2019 11:19 AM

Q9 How would you rate your overall experience at the ESiWACE2 Container Hackathon for Modellers (5=best, 1=poor)

Answered: 11 Skipped: 1

■ 1
 ■ 2
 ■ 3
 ■ 4
 ■ 5

	1	2	3	4	5	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
☆	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	9.09%	90.91%	11	4.91
	0	0	0	1	10		

Q10 How likely are you to recommend and/or attend a future hackathon? (5 = very likely, 1=unlikely)

Answered: 11 Skipped: 1

■ 1
 ■ 2
 ■ 3
 ■ 4
 ■ 5

	1	2	3	4	5	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
☆	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	9.09% 1	90.91% 10	11	4.91